

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FIGHT AGAINST CRIMES RELATED TO THE ILLEGAL TRAFFICKING OF NARCOTIC DRUGS AND PSYCHOTROPIC SUBSTANCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16093544>

Annotation: This article is devoted to the analysis of factors influencing the fight against crimes related to the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The article examines the social, economic, legal, and institutional factors of this type of crime. Special attention will be paid to the legislative framework, the activities of state bodies, international cooperation, and the participation of society in the prevention and fight against crime. The importance of digitalization and the use of modern technologies in the fight against crime is also emphasized. The article concludes with proposals for identifying existing problems and developing effective measures to address this problem.

Keywords: Narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, illicit trafficking, crime control, legislation, social factors, digitalization, international cooperation, government bodies

Large-scale social programs are being developed and implemented in Uzbekistan to promote a healthy lifestyle and enhance the physical, spiritual, and cultural development of our society. Protecting human life and health is one of the social tasks. In this regard, in recent years, the leadership of our state has paid special attention to such a negative social phenomenon as "drug addiction," and the fight against illicit drug trafficking is being carried out. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted the shortcomings in the detection of crimes by internal affairs bodies.

It should be noted that the investigation of crimes involving the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances requires special knowledge and extensive use of scientific and technical information on a number of circumstances relevant to the case.

In his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "Today's rapidly changing world opens up new, great opportunities for humanity and youth. At the same time, it exposes them to various unprecedented evil dangers. Malicious forces are inciting naive children against their parents and homeland, taking their lives. In such a tense and dangerous situation, we - parents, teachers and mentors, the public, and the mahalla - must further increase vigilance and awareness in this matter."

Indeed, today, in the information age, the peoples of the world are reaching new heights of development. However, a number of vices that pose a serious threat to the future of young people still persist in the world. One of these vices is the plague of drug addiction. It is no secret that the ongoing processes of illegal drug cultivation in Afghanistan pose a serious threat not only to the population of this region, but also to the entire world.

The scale and speed of drug addiction worldwide are so strong that they undermine the physical and moral development and future of young people, undermine the social stability of society, disrupt the nation's gene pool, and negatively affect the demographic situation^[1].

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In this regard, Professor K.R. Abdurasulova expresses the following opinion:..."more than two-thirds of drug users are young people under 30. Meanwhile, this category of the population is the core of the productive forces that determine social progress"[\[3\]](#).

Indeed, the prevention of drug trafficking and the fight against drug addiction have become the most pressing problem of the 21st century. During the years of independence, measures to combat drug trafficking crimes have been significantly strengthened in our country, and large-scale preventive work is being carried out.

Analysis of specific social studies shows that the largest group of drug addicts consists mainly of persons aged 16-25, characterized by unfavorable family circumstances, academic failure, conflicts with others, early acquaintance with alcoholic beverages, low education, lack of high professional specialization, dissatisfaction with their position in official communities, involvement in spontaneous groups of minors and youth with antisocial orientation.

By the 21st century, illicit drug trafficking has become a transnational threat to international security and stability. This requires the development of large-scale international cooperation from the world community. Such vices as drug addiction and drug trafficking, along with disrupting the life of society, are becoming a financial support for various modern threats, especially international terrorism. According to reports, the proceeds from illicit drug trafficking constitute the main source of income for international terrorist organizations. According to the analysis, the countries of the world can be divided into several groups in terms of the application of punitive measures for crimes related to the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs.

The first group includes countries with moderate control (Germany, Italy, France, Russia, etc.). The legislation of these states provides for long-term imprisonment for crimes related to the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs.

The second group includes countries such as the USA, Japan, and China, where harsh and severe punishments, even the death penalty, are applied to crimes related to the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

The third group (liberal group) includes the Netherlands. In this country, the fight against crimes related to the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances is carried out in two directions: against heavy and light narcotic drugs. In the Netherlands, narcotic and psychotropic substances that have a strong influence on humans are mainly prohibited. On the contrary, there are certain limitations in the fight against substances that have a weak effect on the body. For example, hemp has been legalized as a mitigating factor, and liability for the use and storage of this substance is not provided for by law.

If we pay attention to statistical data, as a result of the population's addiction to light narcotic drugs, the crime of theft, robbery, and banditry has increased significantly in the

country. After that, the country's government allowed the use of these substances only at home or in specially designated places.

According to the data, today in some countries of the world (Costa Rica, Canada, Colombia, Belgium, etc.) The narcotic drug "marijuana" was introduced into use. In the Czech Republic, citizens are allowed to carry with them a certain amount of marijuana, cocaine, and heroin.

Other factors are also contributing to the sharp increase in drug addiction in the world. That is, high demand for narcotics in some countries, high unemployment rates, uncertainty about the future, constant and chronic stress, and others can be cited. It should be noted that today, when the scourge of drug addiction poses a serious threat to the peace and stability of the world community, protecting our youth from the influence of these vices becomes an urgent task.

According to experts, the following factors contribute to the addiction of young people to drugs:

- inability to express oneself in other activities;
- responsiveness to age;
- self-expression among peers, emotional arousal;
- inability to foresee harmful consequences, etc.

To prevent young people from becoming addicted to drugs in our country, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the proper organization of their free time, engagement in sports, and engaging in useful work. At the same time, it is necessary to regularly conduct preventive measures aimed at combating the spread of narcotics among young people.

Holding these events in cooperation with law enforcement agencies will serve to eliminate various offenses among young people and prevent crimes related to the illegal trafficking of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances. Most importantly, through this, we will achieve the affirmation of a healthy lifestyle in society, the upbringing of a comprehensively developed generation - the future of our country, and the strengthening of our peace and stability.

Drug addiction is a disease caused by the consumption of narcotic and narcotic substances, which arises as a result of the constant use of narcotic substances. According to experts, the physical and mental state of a person with this disease depends on the consumption of the appropriate narcotic substance that suppresses their appetite. Drug addiction causes profound changes in the young organism. The disease develops gradually and is chronic.

Narcotic substances initially evoke feelings of joy, pleasure, and peace of mind, causing intoxication, which gradually turns into illness when consumed.

Drug addiction can be observed in two cases: in the first case, a person becomes addicted to narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances against their will, as a result of negligence. Such addiction often occurs as a result of incorrect use of medications prescribed by a doctor. With the slightest effect, anxiety intensifies, and some patients, in order to get rid of pain, insomnia, and other aspects of the illness, indiscriminately overdose the substance, disregarding the doctor's prescriptions. Such patients, as a rule, notice that the improvement in their condition is due to the drug and continue to take it. And often, complaining about the severity of their condition, they deceive the doctor. The consequences of such behavior are unfavorable, and the use of narcotic substances occurs even if there is little need for them. The

effects of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances on the body increase further, as a result of which the dependence on the narcotic substance increases and it becomes addictive. Unauthorized changes in the dose of the substance and its frequent and prolonged use lead to drug addiction.

The second case is addiction to narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances for the purpose of conscious intoxication. Drug addiction is typically contracted by those who are unrestrained, emotionally weak, weak-willed, imitating others, knowing nothing but to dispel addiction, and extremely selfish. Such people cannot go against their desires. Therefore, they have a strong propensity for intoxication. Drug addiction is rampant. In those affected by this disease, the illness is very severe and usually leads to unexpected negative consequences.

Drug addicts have a desire to repeatedly and in large quantities consume narcotics. Later, they become unable to resist the use of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances, otherwise they feel like "something is missing." To overcome this condition and feel lighter, they resort to drugs or psychotropic substances again. Thus, addiction to narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances arises. Gradually, the addiction to narcotic substances in the body increases to such an extent that the narcotic substances seem to lose their power, and they still want to consume more drugs to dissipate their cravings.

A drug addict will resort to any baseness to get another dose of pleasure, will not hesitate to commit treachery, deception, violence, and theft. If drugs or psychotropic substances do not enter the body, profound mental and physical changes occur. As the disease progresses, the body's exhaustion also increases. The power of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances becomes burdensome for the body. Poisoning is severe, and with a slight increase in the dose of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances, the patient may die.

Drug use, regardless of its type, is a harmful habit that leads to tragic consequences. Its cultivation, sale, purchase, and distribution are prohibited by law. Consequently, the legislation of our country also establishes liability for crimes related to illicit drug trafficking.

Based on this, in preventive work aimed at preventing drug addiction among minors, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- prevention of various offenses committed by minors, effective cooperation in this area with public associations, bodies of citizen self-government, and public organizations;
- involving, along with young people, their parents and relatives in preventive measures carried out on the ground,
- increasing their influential role in society;
- it is advisable to widely involve minors and youth in socially useful work and various sports activities.

In conclusion, the fight against drug addiction and related crime is not only a task facing law enforcement agencies, but also an important task of citizens, as well as enterprises, organizations, institutions, and the public. To prevent our youth from becoming addicted to drug addiction, adults should help them spend their free time properly, pay serious attention to cultural recreation, sports, and engaging in useful work. In this regard, preventive measures called "Combating the Spread of Narcotic Drugs Among Youth" are being carried out in our country.

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